

خلع کے اسباب و اثرات کا جائزہ

A REVIEW OF THE CAUSES AND EFFECTS OF DIVORCE**Dr. Imrana Shahzadi (ORCID ID: 0000-0003-1947-3505)**

Assistant Professor, Department of Arabic, Govt. College Women University, Faisalabad.

Rukhsana Nazeer (ORCID ID: 0009-0005-3765-2904)

M.Phil. Scholar, Deptt. of Islamic Studies, Govt. College Women University, Faisalabad.

ABSTRACT

Islam gives a woman the right to divorce this is called Khulla. A woman is dependent in such a right, she has to concern to court orders. Any kind of domestic violence in the marriage is not acceptable and strongly condemned by Islam. If a woman is suffering domestic violence, impotency of her husband or some adultery and infidelity issues she can proceed to Khulla. While now a days the alarming situation of Khulla in our society has become a cause of great concern.

There are several causes of Khulla and divorce but sadly in most of the cases minor disputes and family grudges are leading towards Khulla. It depicts the miserable condition of a Muslim women in our society. The ratio of Khulla has increased alarmingly in eastern countries and especially in Pakistan. Marriages are breaking like a glass and they are causing bitterness and anxiety in our society. In this article, we will discuss causes and effects of Khulla that lead to bitterness and anxiety.

Keywords: Khulla, Divorce, Separation, Dissolution of Marriage, Marriage failure.

کلیدی الفاظ: خلع، طلاق، علیحدگی، نکاح کا خاتمہ، شادی کی ناکامی۔

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